

Abstract

Nuclear quadrupole resonance spectroscopy is an analytical method which allows to characterize materials which contain quadrupolar nuclei, i. e. nuclei with $spin \geq 1$. The measurement technology is similar to that of NMR except that no static magnetic field is necessary. In contrast to NMR, however, it is frequently necessary to scan spectra with a very large bandwidth with a span of several tens of % of the central frequency so as to localize unknown peaks. Standard NMR probeheads which are typically constructed as resonators must be tuned and matched to comparatively narrow bands and must thus be re-tuned and re-matched very frequently when scanning over a whole NQR spectrum. At low frequencies up to few MHz dedicated circuits without the need for tuning and matching have been developed, but many quadrupole nuclei have transitions in the VHF range between several tens of MHz up to several hundreds of MHz. Currently available commercial NQR probeheads employ stepper motors for setting mechanically tuneable capacitors in standard NMR resonators. These yield high quality factors (Q) and thus high SNR but are relatively large and clumsy and do not allow for fast frequency sweeps. This article presents a new concept for a NQR probehead which combines a previously published no-tune no-match wideband concept for the transmit (TX) pulse with an electronically tuneable receive (RX) part employing varactor diodes. The prototype coil provides a TX frequency range of 57 MHz with a center frequency of 97.5 MHz with a return loss of ≤ -15 dB. During RX the resonator is tuned and matched automatically to the right frequency via control voltages which are read out from a previously generated lookup table, thus providing high SNR. The control voltages which bias the varactors settle very fast and allow for hopping to the next frequency point in the spectrum within less than 100 μ s. Experiments with a test sample of ZnBr₂ proved the feasibility of the method.

Keywords: nuclear quadrupole resonance, wideband probehead, resonator, varactor diodes, tuning and matching